

**BUILDING
MOVEMENT**

**ACHIEVING
TRANSFORMATION**

**11TH
AESOP
SUSTAINABLE
FOOD
PLANNING
CONFERENCE**

**19-22.06.2024
BRUSSELS
& GHENT**

with the support of FWO and AESOP4Food

Organization Team

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Graphic design by Emma Bierens

11TH CONFERENCE

AESOP SUSTAINABLE

FOOD PLANNING

Building Movement, Achieving Transformation

We live in a time of incumbent socio-ecological crises demanding short-term action, but also longer-term and structural transformations. The effects of disruptions such as climate change, environmental degradation, health emergencies, geopolitical conflicts and socio-economic inequities, cannot be ignored. These emergencies have profound effects on urban-regional food movements. On the one hand, they make key food system problems more visible: from emergency food networks escalating across urban areas and reviving food justice concerns, to groups that point to the climate breakdown and call for more ecologically and socially sustainable food production systems. On the other hand, crises are calling for socially innovative initiatives to emerge, envisioning new solutions and advocating for alternative courses of action. As a result, sustainable food planning today needs to actively engage with initiatives on the ground and create socially innovative alliances with the plurality of (food) movements.

Against this background, the 11th AESOP Sustainable Food Planning Conference asks how sustainable food planning can become more embedded in socially innovative and transformative movements, strategically supporting the multiple communities imagining alternatives and mobilizing around the sustainable transformation of food systems.

When considered through a socially innovative and transformative lens, food becomes a driver for changes in deep structures of societies and economies (Holt-Giménez, 2019). Which socially innovative food planning practices are capable of devising creative solutions to unmet needs? How to imagine cooperative and responsible action across diverse agents of the food system and at critical scales? How to build cohesiveness and cooperation without losing sight of the multivocality and diversity of food systems that are necessary to build more resilient societies and urbanities (IPES-Food, 2016)? How to effectively advocate for institutional and planning frameworks that respect the autonomy and creativity of socially innovative food initiatives and encourage alternative forms of food production to take root? How to courageously advance goals of socio-ecological justice as triggers and targets for food systems' transformations?

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Wednesday June 19th, 2024

Time	Location	Session	Facilitators
13.30 - 14.30	Parckfarm	Welcome introduction, explanation Parckfarm and ice-breaking game	Roxana Triboi, Alessandra Manganelli
14.30 - 15.30	Herman Teirlinck, 01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen	Group work on research themes connected to the Conference	
15.30 - 16.00		Break	
16.00 - 17.00		A dialogue with urban food planning scholars and practitioners	
17.00 - 17.30		Closing and next steps in building this group	Roxana Triboi, Alessandra Manganelli

The AESOP-Sustainable Food Planning group aspires to improve the integration of PhD students and young professionals and to grow the “next generation” of experts in the field of sustainable food planning. This resulted in the formalised PhD and young academic professionals group (YAP) of AESOP-SFP. This group wants to improve the integration of PhD students and young professionals and to grow the “next generation” of experts in the field of sustainable food planning.

Throughout the year, the YAP group organises several exchange moments. This year, they are pleased to invite you to a side event they organise on Wednesday, June 19 in Brussels; prior to the AESOP SFP Conference of 2024. The event is open to young professionals, practitioners, PhD students, postdocs, and others interested.

With this workshop, the YAP group aims (similar to their program) to learn new skills, exchange experiences, network, get feedback on working relations, discuss research in progress, and reflect on the (next steps in their) career amongst peers in a relaxed atmosphere.

If you are interested to join this group in the future, please contact:

— Roxana Triboi: roxanatriboi@gmail.com

— Alessandra Manganelli: alessandra.manganelli@hcu-hamburg.de

Parckfarm
Boulevard du Jubilé,
1080 Molenbeek-Saint-Jean

Herman Teirlinck,
Havenlaan 88,
1000 Brussels

Wi-Fi
Vlaamse Overheid Event Netwerk
password: vl#@nderen

Herman Teirlinck,
Tour & Taxis

Havenlaan 88,
1000 Brussels

Thursday June 20th, 2024

Time	Location	Session	Speaker/Chair
09:00 - 09:30	00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte	Registration	
09:30 - 10:00	00.11 Auditorium	Welcome and intro "20 Years of Sustainable Food Planning"	Chiara Tornaghi & Michiel Dehaene
10:00 - 10:45		Keynote "Local food systems in France : is food transforming local public policies?"	Florent Yann Lardic
10:45 - 11:45		Debate on challenges for agriculture policy and visioning in metropolitan regions in France and Belgium	Florent Yann Lardic, Jan Pille, Eva Kerselaers, Christian Jonet & Michiel Dehaene
11:45 - 12:00		Book launch teasers	
12:00 - 13:30	00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte	Lunch , with book presentations	
13:30 - 15:00		Paper Sessions Round 1	
	01.16 Rik Wouters	1.A Productive Landscapes	Elke Vanempten
	01.17 Clara Peeters	1.B Agroecological Urbanism	Marian Simón Rojo
	01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen	1.C Urban Agriculture Practices	Silvio Caputo
	01.21 Jeanne Brabants	1.D Food Mapping Initiatives	Riccardo Bruno
	01.23 Leon Stynen	1.E Intersectionality and Food Justice	Valentine Cadieux
	00.11 Auditorium	1.F Special Panel: Research-Policy-Practice Dialogue with invited speakers	Alessandra Manganelli, Roxana Triboi & Henk Renting
15:00 - 15:15	00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte	Coffee break	
15:15 - 16:45		Paper Sessions Round 2	
	01.16 Rik Wouters	2.A City Region Food Systems	Henk Renting
	01.17 Clara Peeters	2.B Movement Building Across the Food System	Chiara Tornaghi
	01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen	2.C Community Gardening	Ivonne Weichold
	01.21 Jeanne Brabants	2.D Design Strategies for Sustainable Foodscapes	André Viljoen
	01.23 Leon Stynen	2.E Urban Food in Times of Crisis	Amber Steyaert
	00.11 Auditorium	2.F Experimenting with Urban Food Governance	Alessandra Manganelli, Luca Battisti & Federico Cuomo
	00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte	AESOP4FOOD Seminar	Jeroen de Vries & Roxana Triboi
16:45 - 17:00		Coffee break	
17:00 - 18:00		Keynote "A critical reflection on urban food governance "transformations""	Ana Moragues Faus
18:00 - 19:00		Travel to BelMundo	
19:00	BelMundo Henegouwenkaai 41-43 Sint-Jans-Molenbeek	Conference Dinner and guided tour	

Wi-Fi
 Vlaamse Overheid Event Netwerk
 password: vl#@nderen

Friday June 21st, 2024

Time	Location	Session	Speaker/Chair
09:30 - 10:00	Entrance, STAM	Registration	
10:00 - 10:30	Abdijrefter, STAM	Welcome and intro "Why are we in Ghent? A word on the expo 'Gentse Gronden'"	Hans Vandermaelen
10:30 - 12:00		Paper Sessions Round 3	
	Abdijrefter, STAM	3.A Public Farmland and Public Policy	Michiel Dehaene
	Baudelo, STAM	3.B Strategies of Movement Building	Tomaso Ferrando
	Placidus, STAM	3.C Urban Agriculture Frameworks	Jan Eelco Jansma
	Auditorium B, Rommelaere	3.D Urban Food Environments	Carla Mingolla
	Auditorium C, Rommelaere	3.E Food Procurement, Redistribution and Welfare	Florent Lardic
	Auditorium D, Rommelaere	3.F Role of Local Governments	Alessandra Manganeli
	Entrance, STAM	Guided tour exhibition	
12:00 - 13:30	Entrance, STAM	Lunch	
13:30 - 15:00		Paper Sessions Round 4	
	Abdijrefter, STAM	4.A Peri-urban Dynamics	Coline Perrin
	Baudelo, STAM	4.B Moving with the Farmers	Daniel López García
	Placidus, STAM	4.C From Informal to Formal Urban Agriculture	Silvio Caputo, Michael Hardman & Chris Blythe
	Auditorium B, Rommelaere	4.D Training and Policy Learning	Jeroen de Vries
	Auditorium C, Rommelaere	4.E Landed Community Kitchens with invited speakers	Chiara Tornaghi & Charlotte Prové
	Auditorium D, Rommelaere	4.F Experimenting for Food Equity	Marian Simón Rojo
	Entrance, STAM	Guided tour exhibition	
15:00 - 15:15	Entrance, STAM	Break	
15:15 - 16:15	Abdijrefter, STAM	Keynote "How is sustainable food planning contributing to agroecological repair?"	Valentine Cadieux
16:15 - 17:15	Entrance, STAM or outside in the garden	Co-creative session "Building an agenda for Sustainable Food Planning"	
17:15 - 17:30		Closing of the Conference	

Wi-Fi
at STAM: free Wifi City of Ghent
at Rommelaere: use eduroam or UGent Guest

Fieldtrip
Start: Metro
"Eddy Merckx"

Saturday June 22nd, 2024

Time	Location	Session	Speaker
09.00 - 09.30	Metro stop "Eddy Merckx"	Meeting point	
09.30 - 12.30		Guided Walk Neerpede (6,5km)	Catherine Fierens
12.30 - 13.30	Kattekasteeel	Lunch	
13:30 - 15:00	Rue Chant d'Oiseaux 171, 1070 Anderlecht	Visit Espace Test Site 'Graines de Paysans (Espace-test Agricole)'	Gabriele Annicchiarico

In the Neerpede valley, the project of 'Boeren Brussel Paysans' aims to realise production, processing and distribution projects in a short supply chain for local, healthy and quality food accessible to all residents of the capital. The field visit will allow to explore efforts to protect land and develop agro-ecological agriculture, together with the triggers for a re-localised food system in the peri-urban area of Brussels. As part of the BoerenBrusselPaysans project Brussels Capital Region invested in the establishment of a 'test farm' for neo-farmers. We will visit this farm at the end of the fieldtrip.

More info about Boeren Brussel Paysans can be found on [here](https://environnement.brussels/pro/nos-actions/projets-et-resultats/boerenbrusselpaysans-vers-une-agriculture-peri-urbaine-durable): <https://environnement.brussels/pro/nos-actions/projets-et-resultats/boerenbrusselpaysans-vers-une-agriculture-peri-urbaine-durable> or in their publication "[Agropolis – From Pilot Project to Metropolitan Food Network](#)".

Our guide, **FIERENS Catherine**, trained as an architect and practised architecture, landscape architecture, public space and political consultancy before becoming involved with Brussels Environment. Since 2015, she has coordinated the ERDF project BoerenBrusselPaysans. She is interested in the shaping of the city and its ecological transition, in which food systems have a major impact.

An anthropologist by training, **ANNICCHIARICO Gabriele** has coordinated several urban, social and professional agriculture projects in Italy and Belgium. He is currently responsible for coordinating the agricultural test space "Graines de paysans" (Début des Haricots asbl / BoerenBrusselPaysans) in Brussels. As a journalist for the Italian print media (il Manifesto), he covers Belgian and European politics with particular focus on sustainable agriculture and food.

BOOK

OF

ABSTRACTS

Overview of Paper Sessions

Track A
**Spatial Planning,
Soil and Land**

Track B
**Agroecology and
Movement Building**

Track C
**Forms of Urban
Agriculture**

Thursday 20.06.2024
Brussels

13.30 - 15.00

Paper session round 1

1.A
**PRODUCTIVE
LANDSCAPES**
Room:
01.16 Rik Wouters
Session chair:
Elke Vanempten

1.B
**AGROECOLOGICAL
URBANISM**
Room:
01.17 Clara Peeters
Session chair:
Marian Simón Rojo

1.C
**URBAN AGRICULTURE
PRACTICES**
Room:
01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen
Session chair:
Riccardo Bruno

15.15 - 16.45

Paper session round 2

2.A
**CITY REGION FOOD
SYSTEMS**
Room:
01.16 Rik Wouters
Session chair:
Henk Renting

2.B
**MOVEMENT BUILDING
ACROSS THE FOOD
SYSTEM**
Room:
01.17 Clara Peeters
Session chair:
Chiara Tornaghi

2.C
**COMMUNITY
GARDENING**
Room:
01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen
Session chair:
Ivonne Weichold

Friday 21.06.2024
Ghent

10.30 - 12.00

Paper session round 3

3.A
**PUBLIC FARMLAND
AND PUBLIC POLICY**
Room:
Abdijrefter, STAM
Session chair:
Michiel Dehaene

3.B
**STRATEGIES OF
MOVEMENT BUILDING**
Room:
Baudelo, STAM
Session chair:
Tomaso Ferrando

3.C
**URBAN AGRICULTURE
FRAMEWORKS**
Room:
Placidus, STAM
Session chair:
Jan Eelco Jansma

13.30 - 15.00

Paper session round 4

4.A
**PERI-URBAN
DYNAMICS**
Room:
Abdijrefter, STAM
Session chair:
Coline Perrin

4.B
**MOVING WITH THE
FARMERS**
Room:
Baudelo, STAM
Session chair:
Daniel López García

4.C
**FROM INFORMAL
TO FORMAL URBAN
AGRICULTURE**
Room:
Placidus, STAM
Session chair:
Silvio Caputo, Michael
Hardman & Chris Blythe

Track D
**Mapping, Strategizing
and Design**

Track E
**Perspectives on Food
Justice**

Track F
**Food Governance and
Experimentation**

Other sessions

1.D
**FOOD MAPPING
INITIATIVES**

Room:
01.21 Jeanne Brabants
Session chair:
Silvio Caputo

1.E
**INTERSECTIONALITY
AND FOOD JUSTICE**

Room:
01.23 Leon Stynen
Session chair:
Valentine Cadieux

1.F
**SPECIAL PANEL
RESEARCH-POLICY-
PRACTICE DIALOGUE**

Room:
00.11 Auditorium
Session chair:
Alessandra Manganelli,
Roxana Triboi & Henk
Renting

2.D
**DESIGN STRATEGIES
FOR SUSTAINABLE
FOODSCAPES**

Room:
01.21 Jeanne Brabants
Session chair:
André Viljoen

2.E
**URBAN FOOD IN
TIMES OF CRISIS**

Room:
01.23 Leon Stynen
Session chair:
Amber Steyaert

2.F
**EXPERIMENTING
WITH URBAN FOOD
GOVERNANCE**

Room:
00.11 Auditorium
Session chair:
Alessandra Manganelli, Luca
Battisti & Federico Cuomo

**AESOP4FOOD
SEMINAR**

Room:
00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte
Session chair:
Jeroen de Vries & Roxana
Triboi

3.D
**URBAN FOOD
ENVIRONMENTS**

Room:
Auditorium B, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Carla Mingolla

3.E
**FOOD
PROCUREMENT,
REDISTRIBUTION AND
WELFARE**

Room:
Auditorium C, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Florent Lardic

3.F
**ROLE OF LOCAL
GOVERNMENTS**

Room:
Auditorium D, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Alessandra Manganelli

**GUIDED TOUR
EXHIBITION**

Room:
Entrance, STAM

4.D
**TRAINING AND
POLICY LEARNING**

Room:
Auditorium B, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Jeroen de Vries

4.E
**LANDED COMMUNITY
KITCHENS**

Room:
Auditorium C, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Chiara Tornaghi &
Charlotte Prové

4.F
**EXPERIMENTING FOR
FOOD EQUITY**

Room:
Auditorium D, Rommelaere
Session chair:
Marian Simón Rojo

**GUIDED TOUR
EXHIBITION**

Room:
Entrance, STAM

Track A Spatial Planning, Soil and Land

<p>1.A PRODUCTIVE LANDSCAPES p. 36 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 01.16 Rik Wouters</p>	<p>Session Chair Elke Vanempten</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Milan's agricultural districts: food landscape laboratories? — Urbanising Food Landscapes: Planning Food Systems Transformation for Sustainability in Central Algarve, Portugal — New Agricultural Parks regenerating city-region landscapes — Top down and bottom-up circular food initiatives and continuous productive urban landscapes - A critical reflection on the potential to scale circular initiatives for systemic change in city regions 	<p>Paola Branduini Sebastian Burgos Guerrero Maciej Łepkowski André Viljoen</p>
<p>2.A CITY REGION FOOD SYSTEMS p. 52 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 01.16 Rik Wouters</p>	<p>Session Chair Henk Renting</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — The role of participative foresight in creating a sustainable food supply for the Brussels-Capital Region — Territories of urban-rural hybridisation in the agro-ecological transition. A spatial exploration of agro-ecology initiatives in Veneto plain — Strategizing regional food systems as pathways towards sustainability transitions: The case of Lisbon's Metropolitan Area — Global city goes local: State ambitions and societal undercurrents of food localization in Singapore 	<p>Hannelore De Schaepmeester Alessandra Marcon Rosário Oliveira Emily Soh</p>
<p>3.A PUBLIC FARMLAND AND PUBLIC POLICY p. 72 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Abdijrefter, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Michiel Dehaene</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Perceptions of, and barriers to, urban food growing: Informal food growing and access to public land. Examples from the UK — Roles of Local Governments in the Governance of Agricultural Land in France — Public urban agriculture equipment for sustainable food systems: the necessary mobilization of multiple public policies — A cartography of change: Public farmland as a catalyst for sustainable food planning 	<p>Chris Blythe Coline Perrin Véronique Saint-Ges Glenn Willems</p>
<p>4.A PERI-URBAN DYNAMICS p. 90 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Abdijrefter, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Coline Perrin</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Proximity Agriculture in Underdeveloped Urban Areas: A Case Study in Matosinhos, Northern Portugal — Agri-food chains in marginal areas: an occasion for systemic policy experimentation — Progressive Loss of Agricultural Land in Agglomerations: A Case Study of Poznań, Poland — Socio-metabolic approach to urban and rural links - operationalization through alternative food initiatives 	<p>Heloisa Amaral Antunes Anna Fera Ewa Kacprzak & Barbara Maćkiewicz Mehmet Can Yilmaz</p>

Track B Agroecology and Movement Building

<p>1.B AGROECOLOGICAL URBANISM p. 39 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 01.17 Clara Peeters</p>	<p>Session Chair Marian Simón Rojo</p>
<p>— Unlocking the agroecological potential of Lucanian farming and food practices</p>	<p>Ilaria Boniburini</p>
<p>— Urban rooftop farming in Brussels: an analysis from an agroecological point of view</p>	<p>Francisco Davila</p>
<p>— Assessing the agroecological performance and sustainability of Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) farms in Flanders, Belgium</p>	<p>Ruben Savels</p>
<p>— Agroecologies: Reassess Urbanisation Through Agri-Urban Design</p>	<p>Ivonne Weichold</p>
<p>2.B MOVEMENT BUILDING ACROSS THE FOOD SYSTEM p. 55 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 01.17 Clara Peeters</p>	<p>Session Chair Chiara Tornaghi</p>
<p>— Agroecological urbanism for an urban future. Bottom-up Transitions: evidence from Nilüfer, Turkey</p>	<p>Mehmet Can Yılmaz</p>
<p>— Addressing the role and policy needs of Agroecology-Oriented Farmers Groups in transforming food systems</p>	<p>Daniel López García</p>
<p>— Connecting movements by pluralizing the governance of city-region food system transformations in (former) centres of colonial Europe: A relational review of encounters between the visions, protagonists, and governance practices of decolonial, food justice, food sovereignty and sustainability transition movements</p>	<p>Tobia Jones</p>
<p>— Tackling food poverty! Towards healthy, sustainable and socially just food environments through inclusive participation</p>	<p>Evelyn Markoni</p>
<p>3.B STRATEGIES OF MOVEMENT BUILDING p. 75 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Baudelo, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Tomaso Ferrando</p>
<p>— Thinking through landscape frictions: unlocking the transformative power of permaculture projects</p>	<p>Leila Chakroun</p>
<p>— The challenges to build prefigurative food movements: critical reflections from the experience of SPGs in Italy</p>	<p>Cecilia Cornaggia</p>
<p>— Building Community Resilience through a Civic Hub: A Case Study of the “Civic Pole” Project in the 8th district of Rome</p>	<p>Francesca Felici</p>
<p>— Exploring the Dynamics of University-Led Communities of Practice in Shaping Food Democracy</p>	<p>Amber Steyaert</p>
<p>4.B MOVING WITH THE FARMERS p. 93 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Baudelo, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Daniel López García</p>
<p>— Centering Indigenous Knowledge and Values in the Development of Integrated Agroecological Renewable Energy Systems</p>	<p>Diana Denham</p>
<p>— Promoting Farmers’ Innovation for Food Security and Agrobiodiversity</p>	<p>Saurav Ghimire</p>
<p>— Resisting the agro-industrial model. Building food autonomy from a territory of conflict</p>	<p>Alessandra Miglio</p>
<p>— How Farmers Disentangle from Convention and Develop Social and Ecological Objectives in Lincolnshire</p>	<p>Yonatan Weinberg</p>

Track C Forms of Urban Agriculture

<p>1.C URBAN AGRICULTURE PRACTICES p. 42 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen</p>	<p>Session Chair Riccardo Bruno</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Towards a European Urban Agriculture Policy and Governance Framework. Learning from the Roman experience — Agricultural practices in French prisons : towards better agro-ecological environments — The City's Low Hanging Fruits 	<p>Elisabetta Luzzi, Patricia Lelli</p> <p>Daniela Sias</p> <p>Neta Vardi</p>
<p>2.C COMMUNITY GARDENING p. 59 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 01.19 Paul Van Ostaijen</p>	<p>Session Chair Ivonne Weichold</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Learning from community gardens: designing an inclusive planning process in the periurban area of Bucharest — Uneven Recognition: Community Gardens or Allotments? — Community gardens as a response to the contradictions of sustainable urban policy: Insights from the Swiss cities of Zurich and Lausanne — A New Growing Season: Socially Innovative and Transformative Gardening Practices in London 	<p>Ioana Enache</p> <p>Alban Hasson</p> <p>Ingrid Jahrl</p> <p>Pieter Ooghe</p>
<p>3.C URBAN AGRICULTURE FRAMEWORKS p. 78 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Placidus, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Jan Eelco Jansma</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Urban agriculture and support from local authorities: the case study of Brussels — Contributions of urban agriculture intensification to ensure a sustainable and equitable food security – a systematic literature review — Mapping and exploring the role of Urban Agriculture in EU policy discourses and practices: From invisible practices to leverage point for food system integration? — LET'S GROW TOGETHER! – The European Forum on Urban Agriculture (EFUA) Manifesto 	<p>Léna De Brabandere</p> <p>Ann-Kristin Steines</p> <p>Henk Renting</p> <p>EFUA</p>
<p>4.C FROM INFORMAL TO FORMAL URBAN AGRICULTURE p. 96 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Placidus, STAM</p>	<p>Session Chair Silvio Caputo, Michael Hardman, Chris Blythe</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Reviving the educational garden – unfolding an ambiguous pathway for political recognition — Grey areas and green spaces: revealing the conflicts and gaps in the formalisation process of urban agriculture in Bogotá — Educational and advisory services for urban and peri-urban agriculture: Informal and formal tools for enabling knowledge and innovation — Edible Streets - Proposing semi-formal urban food growing 	<p>Trine Carstensen</p> <p>Valentina Manente</p> <p>Joe Nasr</p> <p>Mina Samangoeei</p>

Track D Mapping, Strategizing and Design

1.D FOOD MAPPING INITIATIVES	Session Chair
p. 45 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 01.21 Jeanne Brabants	Silvio Caputo
— Mapping the urban food movement through its people	Katrin Bohn
— Bringing about change in urban planning: how action research put urban agriculture on the map in the planning of peri-urban Oosterwold (NL)	Jan Eelco Jansma
— The University as a Critical Player of the Urban Food Policies. Towards a Food Atlas for the City of Trieste	Valentina Rodani
— Productive images	Noël van Dooren

2.D DESIGN STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE FOODSCAPES	Session Chair
p. 62 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 01.21 Jeanne Brabants	André Viljoen
— The Architecture of Sustainable University Foodscape. Design Strategies and Practices for re-shaping the Food-City Nexus	Sara Basso
— The wobbly bridge of design for food. Evaluating the potential of spatial design to bridge the realms of agriculture and planning	Jeroen De Waegemaeker
— Gaps in urban food systems in Portugal: Lessons learned from 91 projects funded by national authorities	João Pratas

3.D URBAN FOOD ENVIRONMENTS	Session Chair
p. 81 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Auditorium B, Rommelaere	Carla Mingolla
— Exploring the Rural-Urban Continuum of Food Poverty in the Metropolitan city of Rome	Francesca Felici
— Examining the influence of built and food environments on the quality of children's diets. Insights from the city of Avignon	Camille Horvath
— Food desert of alternative consumption spaces in European cities	Laura Fernández Casal
— How people navigate the foodscape? Analyzing the diversity of households' food procurement practices	Simon Vonthron

4.D TRAINING AND POLICY LEARNING	Session Chair
p. 99 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Auditorium B, Rommelaere	Jeroen de Vries
— New Actors in Metropolitan Food Governance. The Potential role of Museums and Ecomuseums	Nunzia Borrelli
— Raising urban planners' awareness for integration better food and agriculture-related measures into Climate Strategies and Plans – Lessons learned from the Portuguese campaign	Cecília Delgado
— Design possibilities for rooftop agriculture: reflections on two decades of pedagogy, policy and practice in Toronto	June Komisar

Track E Perspectives on Food Justice

1.E INTERSECTIONALITY AND FOOD JUSTICE p. 48 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 01.23 Leon Stynen	Session Chair Valentine Cadieux
— Narratives of Change: more than individual intentions in the path to a sustainable and socially just food future	Patrícia Abrantes
— Urban food governance's potential for a gender-just food transition: preliminary results from fieldwork in Milan and Barcelona	Chiara Bergonzini
— Intersectional Exploration for Food Justice Initiatives in France	Manon Lalliot
— "Good Food" for all? (Re)centering immigrant food justice in urban food policy	Isabela Vera

2.E URBAN FOOD IN TIMES OF CRISIS p. 65 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 01.23 Leon Stynen	Session Chair Amber Steyaert
— Urban Agriculture and Forced Displacement: A Framework for Food Equity and Empowerment	Andrew Adam-Bradford
— Transforming Food Systems in Lebanon: A Tale of Two Alternative Food Models in the Time of Crisis	Sherin Assaf

3.E FOOD PROCUREMENT, REDISTRIBUTION AND WELFARE p. 84 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Auditorium C, Rommelaere	Session Chair Florent Lardic
— Greening school meals: towards a public food system? Case studies from Normandy (France)	Morgane Esnault
— What role for small retailers in urban cross-sectoral partnerships for food redistribution? Evidence from Italy	Stefano Quaglia
— Re-imagining foodspaces-welfare nexus across scales: building proximity networks	Camilla Venturini

4.E LANDED COMMUNITY KITCHENS p. 102 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Auditorium C, Rommelaere	Session Chair Chiara Tornaghi & Charlotte Prové
— Landed Community Kitchens: bringing together good food and food justice for all	Chiara Tornaghi
— with invited speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none">— Prove Charlotte - Urban Academy— Buxant Jennifer - University of Liege— Rijckaert Alix - Kom à la Maison— Vandemoortele Isolde - Urban Tractor— Daems Amelie - Cuisine de Quartier— Allemeersch Leontien - DeKoer	

Track F Food Governance and Experimentation

<p>1.F SPECIAL PANEL: RESEARCH-POLICY-PRACTICE DIALOGUE p. 51 Thu 20.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - 00.11 Auditorium</p>	<p>Session Chairs Alessandra Manganelli, Roxana Triboi & Henk Renting</p>
<p>— Bridging City-Region with Multilevel Governance for Food System Transformation: A Research-Policy-Practice Dialogue</p> <p>— with invited speakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Calori Andrea, Està and Italian Network on urban food policies; — Coste Madeleine, EUROCITIES; — Heidelbach Olaf, DG AGRI — Moyaert Wim, European Coordination Via Campesina — Schauvliege Joke, BE/EPP, NAT rapporteur on Sustainable food systems framework law 	
<p>2.F EXPERIMENTING WITH URBAN FOOD GOVERNANCE p. 67 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 00.11 Auditorium</p>	<p>Session Chairs Alessandra Manganelli, Luca Battisti & Federico Cuomo</p>
<p>— The role of evaluation and learning in innovative food governance</p> <p>— The role of food movements in catalyzing Urban Food Policies. The Punto al Cibo network in Torino</p> <p>— Navigating Hybrid Governance Tensions in Alternative Food Networks: A Case Study of 'La Ceinture Aliment-Terre Liégeoise' in Liège, Belgium</p>	
<p>3.F ROLE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS p. 87 Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Auditorium D, Rommelaere</p>	<p>Session Chair Alessandra Manganelli</p>
<p>— What planning capacities do municipalities have to promote resilient regional food systems?</p> <p>— Navigating Urban Food Governance: Insights from Food Policy Councils in the United States</p> <p>— Food system transformation pathways on hold. Why can local food policies get stuck?</p> <p>— Thematic Food Partnership from Urban Agenda for the EU: Catalyzing Local Food System Transformation in the EU</p>	
<p>4.F EXPERIMENTING FOR FOOD EQUITY p. 103 Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Auditorium D, Rommelaere</p>	<p>Session Chair Marian Simón Rojo</p>
<p>— Urban Gardening Valuation: Unraveling the Nexus with Food Justice in Dortmund, Germany</p> <p>— Post-Growth Metabolism: Rethinking Urban Planning and the role of Open Municipal Markets</p> <p>— Public food markets; inclusive community hubs for just food systems</p> <p>— Urban Agriculture, Land, and Environmental Justice in San Diego, California</p>	

Other sessions

AESOP4FOOD Seminar

p. 69 Thu 20.06.24 - 15.15-16.45 - 00.07 Polyvalente Ruimte

— Fostering Transformation through Blended Learning: The AESOP4Food programme

Jeroen de Vries &
Roxana Triboi

Guided Tour Exhibition “Gentse Gronden”

Fri 21.06.24 - 10.30-12.00 - Entrance, STAM

Fri 21.06.24 - 13.30-15.00 - Entrance, STAM

— Registration for the guided tours, with limited capacity, can be done at the registration desk on Friday.

Food desert of alternative consumption spaces in European cities

Food deserts is a term referring to geographic areas where access of residents to affordable, healthy food is restricted or nonexistent due to varied reasons such as the absence of affordable grocery stores within walkable distance. This study aims to identify the baseline situation of food deserts of alternative consumption spaces that have no or limited access to current Alternative Food Initiative (AFIs) within 12 FUSILLI* cities Living Lab (LLs) borders before the implementation of LLs projects. 'At the core of FUSILLI projec, there are 12 LLs in 12 different cities, whose main objective is to develop urban food plans within their local contexts to achieve an integrated and safe holistic transition towards healthy, sustainable, secure, inclusive and cost-efficient food systems.'** The selection of AFIs is based on the quality and ecological concern of accessible food.

The methodology relies on buffer (radius) technique that calculates Euclidian distance from the geographical location of a food space in ArcGIS. The buffers corresponding to the accessible service area of a food space are calculated based on 400m and 800m radius from the AFIs locations representing the 5-minute and 10-minute walking distance. The borders of the calculation are determined to FUSILLI Living Lab borders consisting of AFIs, which differs from city to city that is the whole city in some cases or a neighborhood border area for some others.

The data used in this study is primarily collected for studies done in FUSILLI leaded by Izmir Democracy University. Data primarily depends on the geographical locations of AFIs which are alternative consumption spaces to represent affordable healthy food spaces in each city. AFNs are exemplified with some examples e.g., consumer cooperatives, ecology collectives, buyers' club, community supported agriculture groups, organic bazaars, farmers' market etc.

We calculate the data at city level as the calculation of total area of food desert within LLs as sub-regions in each city. It is seen that except Athens and Torino, averagely % 75 of LL areas is food desert in 10 cities.

This study depends on the FUSILLI project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000717.

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keywords

— food deserts
— accessibility
— alternative food systems

How people navigate the foodscape? Analyzing the diversity of households' food procurement practices

VONTHRON Simon, PhD, is researcher in geography at INRAE. He works on food access inequalities. More specifically, his research focuses on foodscapes, the spatial practices of household food provisioning and the effect of planning and transport policies on these landscapes and practices.

PERRIN Coline, PhD, is researcher in geography at INRAE. She works on agricultural land and inequalities in food systems.

SOULARD Christophe-Toussaint, PhD, is researcher in

authors

Although the food environment is thought to affect food behaviors, studies' results are inconsistent (Dixon et al. 2021). Beyond the heterogeneity of the methods used (Bivoltsis et al. 2018), different studies underline the importance of individuals' perception of their food environment on their practices (i.e. MacNell et al. 2017; Gravina et al. 2020). It is necessary to look beyond the causal analysis of the relationships between the spatial distribution of food outlets and individual food practices. We need to study how people navigate their food environment, thus moving to a foodscape approach (Vonthron et al. 2020).

In this study, we investigated how people organize themselves practically, in time and space, to procure food. We conducted semi-structured interviews with 27 households in the Montpellier-city region, France. We then analyzed their food procurement practices, the reasons and the meaning they give for their choices and their practices.

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